

CAUSES, CLINICAL SYMPTOMS, AND CLINICO-MORPHOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF CERVICAL EROSION IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

Sadullayeva Laziza Erkinjonovna

Asian International University.

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Abstract. This article describes the fact that the above-described cervical erosion in women of reproductive age begins to develop from cells of a certain type of tissue, at the same time the process grows rapidly, covers neighboring organs and tissues, and provides information about clinical symptoms. Directly for these reasons, the stages of pathology also differ. It is stated that each has its own clinical picture and symptomatology.

Cervical diseases are of great clinical importance for women's reproductive health. This topic reviews the main types of cervical diseases, their symptoms, diagnostic methods, and treatment methods. In particular, pathologies such as cervical cancer, erosion, polyps, stenosis, inflammatory diseases, and HPV infection are analyzed. Cervical cancer is associated with human papillomavirus (HPV), and the importance of Pap tests and HPV tests in early diagnosis is emphasized. The clinical symptoms of erosion and polyps, as well as the consequences of inflammatory processes, are also covered. Cervical pathologies not only increase the risk of oncology, but can also cause problems such as infertility and pregnancy loss.

Keywords: Cervical cancer, erosion, HPV infection, endometrium, myometrium.

ПРИЧИНЫ, КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ СИМПТОМЫ И КЛИНИКО-МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЭРОЗИИ ШЕЙКИ МАТКИ У ЖЕНЩИН РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ВОЗРАСТА.

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается тот факт, что вышеописанная эрозия шейки матки у женщин репродуктивного возраста начинает развиваться из клеток определенного типа ткани, при этом процесс быстро растет, охватывает соседние органы и ткани, и дается информация о клинических симптомах. Непосредственно по этим причинам различаются и стадии патологии. Указывается, что каждая имеет свою клиническую картину и симптоматику.

Заболевания шейки матки имеют большое клиническое значение для репродуктивного здоровья женщин. В данной теме рассматриваются основные виды заболеваний шейки матки, их симптомы, методы диагностики и методы лечения. В частности, анализируются такие патологии, как рак шейки матки, эрозия, полипы, стеноз, воспалительные заболевания и ВПЧ-инфекция. Рак шейки матки связан с вирусом папилломы человека (ВПЧ), и подчеркивается важность Пап-тестов и ВПЧ-тестов в ранней диагностике.

Также освещаются клинические симптомы эрозии и полипов, а также последствия воспалительных процессов. Патологии шейки матки не только увеличивают риск онкологии, но и могут вызывать такие проблемы, как бесплодие и потеря беременности.

Ключевые слова: Рак шейки матки, эрозия, ВПЧ-инфекция, эндометрий, миометрий.

Introduction. Cervical erosion is a purulent change in the mucous membrane of the vaginal part of the cervix. This is one of the most common gynecological diseases and, according to statistics, occurs in every sixth woman. In most cases, erosion does not manifest itself in any way. The woman does not experience any unpleasant sensations, leads a normal lifestyle, and only during a regular examination by a gynecologist does she learn that she needs to treat cervical inflammation.

Sometimes the disease manifests itself through:

- abundant discharge of mucous or purulent fluid from the vaginal canal;
- pain during intercourse;
- discharge of fluid mixed with blood (usually characteristic of true erosion).

Anatomical Structure of the Uterus The uterus plays an important role in the female reproductive system and is divided into three main anatomical parts:

Fundus Uteri (Upper part of the uterus):

- This is the upper, wide part of the uterus, which is connected to the fallopian tubes.
- This part expands significantly during pregnancy.

2. Corpus Uteri (Body of the uterus):

- This is the main and largest part of the uterus.
- Its inner layer is lined with the endometrium and is necessary for the development of the fetus.

Cervix Uteri (Cervix Uteri):

- The lower part of the uterus, which is connected to the vaginal canal.
- The cervix consists of an external and internal opening, which changes during ovulation and childbirth. The internal cavity of the uterus consists of three parts:

- Cavita Uteri (Uterine cavity): The place where the fetus develops.
- Canalis Cervicalis (Cervix Canal): Connects the vaginal canal and the uterine cavity.

Ostium Uteri (Internal and external opening of the uterus): Provides for the exit of the mucous membrane during ovulation and the menstrual cycle.

The cervix (cervix uteri) is morphologically divided into two main parts:

Nowadays, cervical cancer is increasingly common among women. Among the factors that contribute to the development of cancer, oncologists include the following:

Clinical Significance of Cervical Diseases The cervix is associated with a number of diseases and pathological conditions, the clinical significance of which is very high:

1. **Cervical Cancer:** A common oncological disease in women, often associated with HPV infection. It is asymptomatic in the early stages, so early diagnosis is very important.

2. **Cervical Erosion:** Occurs as a result of damage to the epithelial layer. Symptoms: vaginal discharge, bleeding, pain during intercourse.

3. **Polyps:** Tumor-like growths that develop in the endocervical canal or exocervix.

Symptoms: bloody discharge, menstrual irregularities.

4. **Cervical Stenosis:** Narrowing of the cervical canal due to trauma or inflammation.

Causes problems with fertility and the menstrual cycle.

5. **Inflammatory Diseases:** Cervicitis (inflammation of the cervix) occurs as a result of infections or sexually transmitted diseases. Symptoms: vaginal discharge, pain in the lower abdomen, fever.

6. **HPV Infection:** HPV causes pathological changes in the cells of the cervix and increases the risk of developing cancer. HPV vaccination is important for prevention.

7. **Injuries During Childbirth:** Tearing or deformation of the cervix during childbirth. This can lead to infertility and other pathologies in the future. Any pathological changes in the cervix can lead to infertility, miscarriage, and other complications. Therefore, early detection and treatment of diseases is important for a woman's overall reproductive health.

Cervical erosion can be: congenital. It is formed due to the protrusion of the cylindrical epithelium beyond the cervical canal. The pathological process occurs in the prenatal period.

Congenital erosion is always small, smooth, surrounds the external throat of the cervix, has a red color. When examining them, the doctor determines whether pathological secretions are released from the cervical canal, whether there are signs of an inflammatory process. Most often, congenital erosion disappears on its own. However, if they persist until adulthood, the risk of infection and subsequent changes in the cervix increases;

Causes of cervical erosion:

Inflammatory diseases of the urinary system are considered to be the cause of cervical erosion.

Gynecologists include the following in the list of factors that cause the problem:

mechanical damage to the cervix (artificial termination of pregnancy, natural childbirth, surgical interventions, etc.);

reduced general / local immunity;

changes in the hormonal background (in pregnant women, in the postpartum period, after the first sexual intercourse);

spermicides.

How to treat cervical erosion

Today, gynecologists prefer methods of treating cervical erosion that destroy cylindrical epithelial cells and help replace them with flat ones. For this, the following are used:

cryodestruction. Erosion tissues are destroyed by freezing. For this, liquid nitrogen/nitrous oxide is applied to their surface.

The method is painless, does not lead to the formation of scars on the cervix. A month after cryodestruction, pathological tissues are completely replaced by healthy tissues;

laser ablation. Using a laser beam, the gynecologist removes pseudo-erosion on the seventh day of the menstrual cycle. It is important that the patient undergoes a special course on vaginal rejuvenation before the procedure.

In general, this method does not cause discomfort and pain. Scars do not form after it, so there will be no problems with conception and childbirth in the future;

diathermocoagulation. Atypical tissues are burned using an electric current of a given frequency.

The complications of such treatment are scars that make the cervix poorly elastic and poorly permeable, so women who have not given birth cannot be treated with this method;

Risk group

Women who have the following conditions are most often affected by cervical erosion:

vaginal dysbiosis, sexually transmitted diseases;

decreased immunity;

early sexual life;

abortion;

hormonal disorders.

Conclusion: to prevent the occurrence of cervical erosion, the following should be observed

To minimize the risk of developing cervical erosion, it is necessary to:

carefully monitor personal hygiene

constantly have only one sexual partner

proper nutrition;

give up bad habits

competent and timely treatment of inflammatory and infectious diseases of the urinary system

et examined by a gynecologist twice a year
get a colposcopy once a year get tested.

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